

Original Article

Developing Prospective Teachers' Time Management Skill at Undergraduate Level

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Abstract

The present study aimed to develop prospective teachers' time management skills at undergraduate level. Present study employed the A-B-A single subject research design. Population of the study consisted of all prospective teachers from department of education, University of Lahore. The study sample was comprised of 18 students from B. Ed. (Hons) Elementary 6th Semester. The experiment consisted of 16 weeks where researcher observed prospective teachers during teaching practice. The observation checklist was used to check the prospective teachers' time management skill in actual classroom setting. Inferential statistics was used to analyze the data. A one-way repeated measures ANOVA was used to determine the significance effect before, during and after the treatment. Findings of present study concluded that a significant effect was found during treatment and withdrawal phase. Prospective teachers significantly develop their time management skill by applying simulation technique. The study recommended to develop prospective teachers' time management skills by employing simulating teaching technique at undergraduate level.

Keywords: Simulated Teaching, Time Management Skill, Prospective Teachers, Undergraduate Level

Introduction

Time management is a common challenge across various professional settings, but it holds particular importance in the teaching profession. Teachers not only manage their own time but also structure the classroom to optimize students' learning experiences. How effectively they manage classroom time directly affects the learning process. Khan, Farooqi, Khalil, and Faisal (2016) stress that time management is just as crucial for teachers as it is for students. It is often associated with concepts like spontaneity, flexibility, balance, and control over one's schedule. In essence, time management involves using strategies that allow individuals to complete tasks and achieve goals efficiently, making the teaching process more effective overall.

According to Khan, Tahir, Ishfaq, and Khan (2017), the two core components of effective time management are planning and scheduling daily priorities. Teachers must clearly define their instructional objectives, plan their lessons accordingly, and tailor their strategies to the needs and level of their students. When time is used purposefully, teaching becomes more structured and impactful.

At the university level, the primary aim is to equip students with the skills necessary for future employment. To fulfill this responsibility, higher education institutions must ensure their graduates are well-prepared for real-world professional settings (Snyder & McNeil, 2008). Today, teachers are expected to possess a broad set of knowledge, skills, and competencies, and to handle multiple roles in increasingly complex classroom environments. High-quality initial teacher education is, therefore, critical. Traditional teacher education programs tend to focus heavily on theory and abstract concepts. To better prepare student-teachers, these programs should also provide practical opportunities to develop the professional skills required in the field. This is particularly important in minimizing the "reality shock" many new teachers experience during their first classroom teaching experiences (Stokking et al., 2003).

Collaborative skills are also essential in today's workforce. These skills should not be learned only on the job; instead, teacher training programs must foster these competencies early. As Snyder and McNeil (2008) argue,

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students must develop teamwork skills before entering professional environments. This need has inspired the development of instructional approaches that emphasize collaboration and practical preparation, helping prospective teachers meet the demands of their future roles.

Within the European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System (ECTS), the emphasis on student autonomy and critical thinking further underlines the importance of time management. ECTS defines student workload as encompassing a range of activities, including readings, group work, individual assignments, and projects (ECTS, 2015). This variety of tasks requires students to manage their academic and personal time effectively. Proper time management enables students to complete all assigned activities, build competencies, and meet learning objectives without experiencing stress, anxiety, or burnout (Romero & Barberà, 2011; Hellsten, 2012; Barberà et al., 2015).

Tortajada et al. (2015) emphasize that effective time management requires the ability to prioritize tasks, distinguish between urgent and non-essential work, avoid procrastination, and persist through difficulties. Students who manage time effectively are more likely to complete tasks with confidence and less psychological strain. In contrast, students who struggle to prioritize often delay tasks and fall behind.

Supporting this, Gallander et al. (2011) and Häfner et al. (2014) found that individuals with training in time management are better at allocating time equitably across tasks and controlling procrastination. Similarly, González-Brignardello and Sánchez-Elvira Paniagua (2013) discovered that students who lack the ability to set priorities are the most likely to procrastinate. Research consistently shows that goal setting and prioritization are directly linked to efficient time use and improved performance (Hellsten, 2012; Darren, 2012).

Objective of the Study

Objective of present study was to develop prospective teachers' time management skill at undergraduate level.

Hypotheses of the Study

- H₀₁:** There is no significant effect of simulated teaching on developing prospective teachers' time management skill during experiment phase.
- H₀₂:** There is no significant effect of simulated teaching on developing prospective teachers' time management skill during withdrawal phase.

Methodology

The present study aimed to develop prospective teachers' time management skill through simulated teaching method at undergraduate level. Present study employed the A-B-A single subject research design. Population of the study consisted of all prospective teachers from Department of Education, University of Lahore. The study sample was comprised of 18 students from B. Ed. (Hons) Elementary 6th semester. The experiment consisted of 16 weeks in which the researcher observed prospective teachers during teaching practice. The observation checklist was developed to check the prospective teachers' time management skill in simulated classroom settings. Inferential statistics was used to analyze the data. A one-way repeated measures ANOVA was used to determine the significance effect of simulated teaching before, during and after the treatment of the experimental group.

Intervention

Three phases were involve implementing this A-B-A design. First phase A, in which the researcher was established a baseline that was also use as dependent variable (prospective teachers' practice about time management skill). The researcher conducted multiple observations during simulated teaching practice of 5th semester, to get the average that creates a baseline on line graph. This was the level of responding before any treatment. It was introduced as the baseline phase a kind of control condition that was provide a comparison after treatment.

Second phase B, was started with intervention. There were two steps involved during implementing the treatment. At first step, the researcher implemented simulated teaching through lecture. During teaching researcher practiced the selected time management skill. It provided an observation to prospective teachers about, how to implement and practice the time management skill in classroom. At second stage of treatment, prospective teachers were practiced time management skill through role-play. During role-play prospective teachers practiced the selected time management skill in an artificial classroom environment, under the researcher's supervision and feedback. Researcher was conducted the observations during role-play performance.

Third phase A was started after treatment withdrawn. When prospective teachers were gone for teacher practice in a real school environment in baseline period. The researcher conducted observations during withdrawal phase. The researcher took three observations of each prospective teacher. The average of the observations was drawn on line-graphs to show the effects of a particular intervention or treatment. Data were analysed using repeated measures ANOVA during baseline period, treatment phase and withdrawal phase during experiment.

Results

Table 1

Mauchly's Test of Sphericity for developing Prospective Teachers' Time Management Skill through Simulated Teaching during Baseline Period

Within Subject Effect	Mauchly's W	Approx. Chi-Square	df	Sig.	Greenhouse-Geisser (Epsilon ^b)
Baseline	.595	8.314	17	.016	.712

Mauchly's sphericity test was used to validate a Repeated Measure Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). Since the .016 significant value is less than that of the critical value 0.05, therefore, it means a significant difference between variances of differences exist of prospective teachers' time management skill during baseline period.

Table 2

Developing Time Management Skill of Prospective Teachers' through Simulated Teaching during Baseline across Three Steps of Intervention

Measures	Baseline Period		
	N	Mean	SD
Observation 1	18	18.55	2.74
Observation 2	18	33.72	9.54
Observation 3	18	23.77	4.25
F	610.160		
df	17		
Sig.	.016		
Partial Eta squared	.973		

The results of table 2 shows that the value of effect of simulated teaching on prospective teachers' time management skill, $F(610.160)$, $p = .016 < .05$ significance level, so our hypothesis H_{02} : "There is no significant effect of simulated teaching on developing prospective teachers' time management skill during baseline period" rejected and it is concluded that the a slightly significant effect of simulated teaching on developing prospective teachers' time management skill was found.

Figure 1

Estimated Marginal Means of Measure

H₀₁: There is no significant effect of simulated teaching on developing prospective teachers’ time management skill during experiment phase.

Table 3

Mauchly’s Test of Sphericity for developing Prospective Teachers’ Time Management Skill through Simulated Teaching during Experiment

Within Subject Effect	Mauchly’s W	Approx. Chi-Square	df	Sig.	Greenhouse-Geisser (Epsilon ^b)
Treatment Phase	.163	27.961	17	.000	.488

Mauchly’s sphericity test was used to validate a Repeated Measure Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). Since the .000 significant value is less than that of the critical value 0.05, therefore, it means prominent significant differences between variances of differences exist.

Table 4

Developing Time Management Skill of Prospective Teachers’ through Simulated Teaching during Experiment across Five Steps of Intervention

Measures	Treatment Phase		
	N	Mean	SD
Observation 1	18	29.72	5.97
Observation 2	18	33.72	9.54
Observation 3	18	34.11	5.47
Observation 4	18	35.72	4.08
Observation 5	18	41.44	4.39
F	1014.323		
Df	17		
Sig.	.000		
Partial Eta squared	.984		

The results of table 4 shows that the value of effect of simulated teaching on developing prospective teachers’ time management skill, $F(1014.323)$, $p = .000 < .05$ significance level, so our hypothesis H₀₂: “There is significant effect of effect of simulated teaching on developing prospective teachers’ time management skill during treatment period” rejected and it is concluded that the significant effect of simulated teaching on prospective teachers’ time management skill was found.

Figure 2

Estimated Marginal Means of Measure

H₀₂: There is no significant effect of simulated teaching on developing prospective teachers' time management skill during withdrawal phase.

Table 5

Mauchly's Test of Sphericity for developing Prospective Teachers' Time Management Skill through Simulated Teaching during Withdrawal

Within Subject Effect	Mauchly's W	Approx. Chi-Square	Df	Sig.	Greenhouse-Geisser (Epsilon ^b)
Withdrawal Phase	.949	.833	17	.000	.952

Mauchly's Sphericity test was used to validate a Repeated Measure Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). Since the .000 significant value is more than that of the critical value 0.05, therefore, it means a prominent difference between variances of differences exist.

Table 6

Developing Time Management Skill of Prospective Teachers' through Simulated Teaching during Experiment across Three Steps of Intervention

Measures	Withdrawal Phase		
	N	Mean	SD
Observation 1	18	42.22	3.43
Observation 2	18	43.38	2.40
Observation 3	18	43.61	2.78
F	15339.342		
df	17		
Sig.	.000		
Partial Eta squared	.999		

The results of table 6 shows that the value of effect of simulated teaching on developing prospective teachers' time management skill, $F(15339.342)$, $p = .000 < .05$ significance level, so our hypothesis H_{03} : "There is significant effect of simulated teaching on developing prospective teachers' time management skill during withdrawal period" rejected and it is concluded that the significant effect of simulated teaching on prospective teachers' time management skill was found.

Figure 3

Estimated Marginal Means of Measure

Discussion

The present study aimed to develop time management skill through simulated teaching method at undergraduate level. The findings of present study indicate that while simulated teaching had no significant impact on prospective teachers' time management skill during the baseline period, it showed a significant effect during the treatment and withdrawal phases. Visual analysis showed that simulated teaching technique has significant effect on prospective teachers' time management skill during baseline, treatment and withdrawal phase. It was observed that prospective

teachers during baseline period did not show a stable behavior regarding their time management in practice teaching. During treatment phase prospective teachers were taught to manage time with the application of simulated teaching technique by the researcher. Therefore, findings of the study revealed that simulated teaching technique has significant effect on prospective teachers' time management skill with the value ($F=1014.323$, $p \leq .000$) at $p \leq .05$ level of significance. During treatment phase prospective teachers learn to come in class on time, took attendance on time, plans the lesson according to the given timeslot, allocate time to activities, took immediate decisions, and encourages students how to manage their time effectively. Effectiveness of simulated teaching was revealed during withdrawal phase when prospective teachers managed their time during practice teaching and showed a stable behavior during practice teaching which did not change even after the removal of treatment. Time management skill also plays a significant role in classroom settings. Present study revealed that prospective teachers also developed time management skill by simulated teaching technique. Time Management is an issue that comes up in all kinds of work environments. Time management can be even more important for teachers since they have a classroom full of students to direct and educate them in the way how they spend their time in class. It is as important to teachers as it is to students (Khan, Farooqi, Khalil & Faisal 2016). Time management has been described by using many different terms including spontaneity, balance, flexibility, and having control over time. Time management has been considered as the process by which an individual can accomplish tasks and goals more effectively. Time management make teaching more effective.

Recommendations

Following were the recommendations of present study.

1. The study findings concluded that simulated teaching has significant effect on students' time management skill. Therefore, it is recommended to create simulations where prospective teachers are given tasks that might be completed within a set time frame, such as preparing lesson plans, grading assignments, or handling classroom management situations.
2. It is recommended to set up role-playing scenarios where prospective teachers need to handle time-sensitive tasks, like responding to an emergency in the classroom or preparing a quick change in lesson plans due to unforeseen circumstances.
3. Provide prospective teachers with opportunities to reflect on their experiences. Have them evaluate how well they managed their time, what strategies worked well, and what areas they could improve on.
4. It is recommended to use group simulations where prospective teachers work together to manage time across multiple classrooms, teaching subjects, or administrative tasks.

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